

Chemical Chaos in a Novel Bromate Driven Oscillator. Thiophenol—Bromate—H₂SO₄ System

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Manuscript received 12 October 1988, accepted 28 February 1989

Chaotic oscillations in redox potential have been observed in thiophenol - BrO₃⁻ - H₂SO₄ system in a batch reactor. These occur in a concentration and temperature range. Bifurcation from the stable regime to chaotic regime occurs straightway in the entire concentration and temperature range. Chaotic oscillations in continuously stirred tank reactor have also been observed at different flow rates. These oscillations are deterministic chaos. It is tentatively suggested that chaos in the systems is due to time delay caused by a large number of intermediates.

CHEMICAL turbulence, chaos or aperiodic oscillations both temporal and spatial have aroused considerable interest ever since it was recognised that chaos is not necessarily a random but deterministic phenomenon¹. Freund *et al.*² have distinguished between deterministic chaos and amplification of experimental noise. The view was reinforced by May³ who suggested a set of difference equations which could generate non-periodicity. Rossler⁴ showed that complex chemical kinetics involving three or more variables can generate chaos. Existence of oscillations and chaos in physiological control system was suggested by Mackey and Glass⁵ based on a model of hematopoiesis (blood cell differentiation). These developments led to experimental search for reactions which could show chaos. First example of chaos in an enzyme reaction was reported by Olsen and Degn⁶. Further, experimental evidence of chaotic state in the B-Z reaction in a CSTR was reported by Schmitz *et al.*⁷. Chaos has been reported in similar system by Heilweil and Epstein⁸. In a certain range of concentration and conditions, chaos has been reported in BrO₃⁻ - ClO₂⁻ - I⁻ system⁹ and ClO₂⁻ - S₂O₈²⁻ system¹⁰. For a certain range of flow rates, chaotic oscillations have been observed in BrO₃⁻ - thiocyanate reaction¹¹. In the systems reported above, chaos could be generated by the control of the flow rate. In this manner a periodicity involving one large amplitude followed by *n* small amplitude of oscillation (*n*=2, 3, 4...) has been achieved. These are examples of period doubling or period multiplicity bifurcation^{10,12} which lead to quasi-periodic oscillations. In some systems, bifurcation from a periodic regime to a aperiodic regime has been reported¹⁰. The example of bifurcation from a stable regime to chaotic regime and vice versa has not been reported so far. In this communication, we report a novel system which is the first example of its kind from this angle.

Experimental

Thiophenol, potassium bromate and H₂SO₄ (AnalaR) were used as oscillatory reactants. The solutions of thiophenol and BrO₃⁻ were prepared in 1.0 M H₂SO₄.

Experimental procedure in batch reactor was similar to that described by Rastogi and Srivastava¹³. Oscillations were studied in the reaction mixture containing 0.004 - 0.15 M thiophenol, 0.022 - 0.038 M BrO₃⁻ and 1.0 M H₂SO₄. In the beginning, on mixing the reagents, the solution was clear. However, within a small time interval it became slightly turbid. Subsequently, the turbidity disappeared and chaotic oscillations were produced. The oscillations were also studied in a continuously stirred tank reactor at different flow rates. The experimental procedure was similar as described earlier¹³. All investigations were performed in a thermostat and the solution was continuously stirred by a magnetic stirrer at 1000 r.p.m. The reaction was followed by recording the redox potential as a function of time, using a bright platinum electrode coupled with reference calomel electrode with an electronic recorder.

The major intermediates indentified by tlc are

products of the reaction by tlc analysis are found to be C₆H₅SO₂H and C₆H₅SO₂Br.

Results and Discussion

The chaotic oscillations in redox potential are obtained in the concentration range 0.004–0.015 *M* thiophenol, 0.022–0.038 *M* BrO_3^- and 1.0 *M* H_2SO_4 in batch reactor. A typical trace at temperature 18° is shown in Fig. 1. There is no Hopf bifurca-

Fig. 1. Chaotic oscillations in batch reactor containing thiophenol (0.012 *M*), BrO_3^- (0.02994 *M*), H_2SO_4 (1.0 *M*) at 18°.

tion. On the other hand, the system bifurcates directly into chaotic regime from the stable branch. On termination of the aperiodic oscillations, the systems bifurcate to stable branch once again. Period doubling beyond the bifurcation point was not observed. Between the two bifurcation points all along chaotic oscillations were found. For the batch reactor, the amplitude of the (*n*+1)th oscillation has been plotted against the amplitude of the *n*th oscillation in Fig. 2 for temperature 18°, which

Fig. 2. A plot of *A*(*n*+1)th amplitude of oscillations against *A* *n*th oscillation at 18°.

shows that Lyapunov exponent is greater than unity. Existence of aperiodic behaviour may be established by utilising Li and Yorke theorem¹⁴. This procedure was used experimentally by Olsen and Degn⁶ to show that chaotic behaviour existed in oscillations of O_2 concentration in a peroxidase catalysed oxidation reaction of NADH. Starting at the critical point (b), in Fig. 2 traced out the next two iterates of the map, $c=f(b)$ and $d=f(c)$,

as well as the pre-image $a, b=f(a)$. Since $a > d$ (i.e., if *d* is to the left of *a*) there exists an infinite number of periodic points and the function can generate aperiodic motion. The Fourier transform of experimental data was performed by the computer; the power spectrum is shown in Fig. 3. It is evident from Fig. 3 that the power spectrum consists of many significant frequencies. From the above arguments it may be conjectured that the observed behaviour is deterministic in nature.

Fig. 3. Power spectrum of experimental data containing thiophenol (0.012 *M*), BrO_3^- (0.02994 *M*) and H_2SO_4 (1.0 *M*) at 18°.

We also observed chaotic oscillations in redox potential in a CSTR at different flow rates k_0 (where k_0 represents reciprocal of residence time) 0.025–0.056 min^{-1} . A typical trace is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Chaotic oscillations in continuously stirred tank reactor containing thiophenol (0.01 *M*), BrO_3^- (0.025 *M*), H_2SO_4 (1.0 *M*) and $k_0=0.04 \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 18°.

It has been suggested that chaos can be generated in an oscillatory system by introducing delay⁸ through the control of the flow rate. It has also been pointed out that similar delay leading to chaos can be obtained in systems where we have more of intermediates^{15,16} in the reaction chain, which is a pre-condition for the existence of chaos.

A tentative mechanism of reaction based on the FKN mechanism¹⁷ can be postulated as follows,

Here it may be noted that $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}^-}{\text{S}}-\text{S}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\overset{\text{O}^-}{\text{S}}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ are in the isomeric form

of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\text{S}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$,

respectively. The reactions (R5) and (R6), and (R7) and (R9) give two autocatalytic reactions in terms of HBrO_2 , as

It is obvious that the reaction chain is complicated and involves a number of pathways and intermediates. The mechanism has some support from the

fact that $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\text{S}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$,

$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{S}}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{H}$ are the inter-

mediates of reactions, and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{H}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{Br}$ are the products of the reaction, as identified by the experiments.

It appears that in the studied system, a number of intermediates, pathways and two autocatalytic reactions are involved which are responsible for the generation of chaos.

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